

CASCADE FUNDING CALL 1

SELECTED PROJECTS OVERVIEW

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Name of the Project	Organisations	Countries	Pages
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General information

In April 2024, the first round of projects was selected as part of the first call for Cascade Funding.

The 25 selected projects introduce diverse starting points and approaches through three types of projects supported. These reflect different stages of an institution's reform journey, namely:

- **Teaming Projects** facilitate knowledge exchange between organizations with different levels of expertise, enabling mutual growth and best practice sharing. These projects are funded up to €40,000 for one year.
- **Institutional Pilot Projects** allow organizations to test new assessment models and approaches in targeted areas, fostering experimentation with tools like IT workflows, qualitative KPIs, and open science metrics. Each project may receive up to €30,000, with a one-year duration.
- **Institutional Change Projects** support more comprehensive reform by refining or creating new assessment structures aligned with the commitments of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. These projects can receive up to €60,000 for a one-year term.

Over 72 applications have been received for the 1st Call of the Cascade Funding, among which, 25 have been selected and supported by CoARA Boost with this following repartition per project type:

Figure 1: Types of Projects Selected for Call 1

With the following geographical diversity of projects per country

Figure 2: Geographical Diversity of Projects per Country for Call 1

In the following pages of the present booklet, each project is introduced with its key elements and the nature of its alignment with the Agreement.

Please note that the projects are not listed or ranked in any order of importance.

List of the Cascade Funding Call 1 Beneficiaries: Teaming Projects

Name of the Project	Organisations	Countries	Pages
Open Science Collaboration for Research Career Advancement and Policy Innovation at UNIRI and UCY (OSCAR)	University of Rijeka University of Cyprus European Office of Cyprus	Croatia Cyprus Cyprus	7
CoARA ExPECT – Exchange & Promote Evaluation Criteria Changes Together	Tampere University Oulu University Rurh Universitat Bochum	Finland Finland Germany	10
Reforming Research Assessment in the University of Carthage Towards a Qualitative Original Approach, Multidisciplinary Model and Sustainable Procedures	University of Carthage Institute for Bioengineering of Catalonia (UBEC)	Tunisia Spain	12

evaluation and responsible use of quantitative indicators, aiming for institutional change and fostering a culture shift towards responsible RA criteria.

Activities involve webinars, workshops, and collaborative sessions for mutual learning and knowledge exchange, with UNIRI's CoARA AP and OS expertise guiding UCY's reform efforts. The project includes scientific validation of RA practices to ensure evidence-based evaluation. The partnership leverages the complementary strengths, with UNIRI's established RA frameworks and UCY's innovative context, ensuring impactful and sustainable reforms. The expected outcomes include improved RA practices at UCY, a shift towards streamlined evaluation methods, enhanced research quality through OS, and broader policy influence. The comprehensive approach and commitment to scientific validation ensure lasting change, benefiting the wider RA community.

Mission and objectives. How does the project fit with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

Mission: foster mutual learning and improvement in Research Assessment (RA) practices at UNIRI (University of Rijeka) and UCY (University of Cyprus) via knowledge exchange, capacity-building, the promotion of Open Science (OS) and the scientific validation of RA.

Objectives: develop an effective CoARA Action Plan (CoARA AP) at UCY, integrate OS into research evaluations, advocate OS at the policy-setting level, support OS through university libraries, and utilise research-on-research to validate and enhance RA practices.

The project carefully aligns with CoARA's vision by integrating its principles into all workplan's aspects and planned outputs, promoting a comprehensive and responsible RA through:

1. acknowledging the diversity of research contributions by incorporating OS practices at organizational and policy-making levels,
2. emphasizing qualitative evaluation supported by peer review, while promoting the responsible use of quantitative indicators,
3. reviewing and developing RA criteria and tools, facilitated by mutual learning and knowledge transfer,
4. raising awareness and providing training on RA reform through webinars, workshops and meetings,
5. facilitating mutual learning via collaborative best practice exchange,
6. transparently communicating and disseminating the outcomes, ensuring all stakeholders are informed on the progress and adherence to CoARA's principles,
7. including scientific validation of policies, methodologies, and practices, ensuring evidence-based evaluation.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Teaming Project selected n°2

Organisation overview	
<p>University of Oulu Oulu, Finland <i>The University of Oulu is one of the largest Finnish multidisciplinary universities, recognised for its research and education in areas such as technology, health sciences, and environmental studies.</i></p> <p><u>Partner organisations:</u> Ruhr University Bochum, Germany <i>Founded in the early sixties to address the challenges of structural change in the region, Ruhr University Bochum has developed into one of Germany's largest research universities. It hosts the full spectrum of academic disciplines on its campus – the humanities and social sciences, the natural sciences and medicine as well as engineering.</i></p> <p>Tampere University, Finland <i>Tampere University is one of the most multidisciplinary universities in Finland, bringing together research and education in technology, health and society.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
CoARA EXPECT – Exchange & Promote Evaluation Criteria Changes Together
Abstract
<p>CoARA EXPECT addresses two interlocked aspects which are at the core of CoARA. Based on the exchange of knowledge and expertise the universities of Oulu, Tampere and Bochum will join forces to raise the awareness for the necessity to reform research assessment.</p> <p>In a first step, exchanging best practices focusing on narrative CVs and infrastructural instruments involved in assessment processes will be shared and discussed across the three universities. The aim is to involve the entire community and get valuable feedback, especially from researchers. At present, the applicant universities already have different mechanisms in place which may help to improve each other's processes in various ways.</p> <p>Additionally, the applicants are very aware that a sustainable and lasting change of research assessment can only be realized with broad acceptance and support within and across the involved institutions. Therefore, sharing and improving best</p>

practices will result in the joint elaboration of guidelines (e.g. in form of checklists, video-pitches and manuals) to further promote the urgency of reforming research assessment and CoARA’s goals and principles. These guidelines will be integrated into processes, advertised and used at the applicant institutions and made available to other CoARA members.

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

CoARA ExPECT is dedicated to advancing the principles of CoARA through the collaborative development and implementation of innovative instructional materials. Our mission is to foster a culture of responsible research assessment that emphasises quality, impact, sustainability and diversity across academic communities. Through our joint effort, we aspire to contribute significantly to the global dialogue on reforming research assessment and to be at the forefront of implementing persistent change that reflects CoARA's values and objectives.

Through utilising high-level expertise in responsible assessment, we aim at creating a suite of joint instructional materials for researchers, evaluators, administrative staff and management of the organisations to facilitate the effective and systematic implementation of CoARA. By creating accessible and engaging instructional videos tailored to address different stages of researcher's career, supported by more detailed written instructions, we will elucidate CoARA's guidelines and best practices and promote a unified approach to research assessment that aligns with CoARA's vision of inclusivity and excellence.

Mutual learning is at the very core of CoARA ExPECT and all parties involved in CoARA (and beyond) are invited and encouraged to freely use the project's results.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project

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- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
- Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
- Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Teaming Project selected n°3

Organisation overview	
<p>University of Carthage (UCAR) Tunis, Tunisia</p> <p><i>UCAR is a leading public multidisciplinary university in Tunisia. The university comprises several faculties, institutes, and schools, spread across various campuses in the Tunis metropolitan area. The university's research projects cover a broad range of fields, including health, energy, environment, and technology. It encourages entrepreneurship, innovation, and finding solutions to local and global challenges.</i></p> <p><u>Partner organisation:</u></p> <p>Institute for Bioengineering of Catalonia (IBEC), Spain</p> <p><i>The Institute for Bioengineering of Catalonia is an institute of excellence combining interdisciplinary research with engineering and life sciences (e.g. nanomedicine, biophysics, biotechnology, tissue engineering) to generate knowledge and produce new applied technologies to be used in life and health sciences.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
<p>Reforming Research Assessment in the University of Carthage Towards a Qualitative Original Approach, Multidisciplinary Model and Sustainable Procedures</p>
Abstract
<p>This project aims to propose, develop, and initiate the implementation of a novel methodology for research assessment at the University of Carthage (UCAR), focusing on criteria such as applicability and dissemination of research findings to partially replace traditional quantitative metrics. In collaboration with the Institute for Bioengineering of Catalonia (IBEC), we aim to develop a more comprehensive qualitative assessment framework that considers the societal and environmental impacts of research and promotes a diverse multidisciplinary research model. The reform model, to be developed and implemented at the Doctoral School of the National Institute of Applied Science and Technology (INSAT) belonging to UCAR, aims to facilitate a fairer and more holistic evaluation of PhD theses, research laboratories, and researchers, thereby fostering innovation and interdisciplinary collaboration. The project underscores</p>

the sustainability of the proposed reform through the standardization of evaluation criteria, resource consolidation, and electronic documentation management. The elaboration of an electronic communication channel will ease the dissemination of project outcomes to all institutions within Carthage University as well as to all universities across Tunisia. In this way, this initiative could make UCAR a pioneer in progressive academic evaluation methodologies, contributing to broader educational and societal advancements.

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

The project aims to pioneer a fresh approach to research evaluation at the UCAR, with focus on the Doctoral School of INSAT.

Prioritizing a qualitative and multidisciplinary framework, this initiative closely aligns with the principles outlined in the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (CoARA). Its primary goal is to assess how research can be practically applied in societal, business, and environmental contexts, with a strong emphasis on broad dissemination of these insights to relevant stakeholders. Indeed, these new evaluation methods will foster multidisciplinary research offering innovative solutions to complex societal problems and enhance career prospects by encouraging collaboration and diversity of skills.

In alignment with CoARA's vision, the project represents a shift away from reliance on publication-based metrics. It supports CoARA's goal of fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and recognizing the broader contributions of research in academic outputs.

Through these efforts, the project proposed by the PMO of UCAR, the Doctoral School of INSAT and IBEC aims to establish a benchmark for responsible and impactful research assessment practices aligned with CoARA's vision, This initiative seeks to uphold academic integrity and significantly contribute to societal advancement by comprehensively evaluating research impact in an inclusive manner.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project

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Institutional Change Project selected n°1

Organisation overview	
<p>Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam Amsterdam, Netherlands</p> <p><i>Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam is a research university offering a wide array of academic programs (humanities, STEM, social sciences and medical sciences) and closely linking education and research.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
Title
<p>IDEA: Integrating Diversity in Evaluation and Assessment of Researchers – Experiences from Amsterdam</p>
Abstract
<p>The Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam’s (VU) Recognition and Rewards (R&R) has implemented measures to enhance research quality, aligning with the COARA agreement. However, the program lacks a focus on equality and inclusiveness, critical principles of this agreement. Research institutions globally face challenges regarding diversity, particularly concerning gender and cultural background representation at higher academic ranks. The VU Diversity Office (DO) has a strategy on ameliorating this at the VU, but collaboration between the R&R program and the DO is crucial to tackle barriers hindering career advancement. Additionally, cooperation with other European institutions is essential for mutual learning, especially as the importance of reforming research assessment to be more inclusive and equitable is gaining attention with developments such as the Cape Town Statement on Research Integrity.</p> <p>This project will integrate diversity into VU's research assessment reforms by aligning efforts between the VU R&R program, DO, and initiatives across Europe. The primary goal is to develop a concrete action plan on how to increase researcher diversity through researcher assessment at the VU. This will be done together with researchers and other research stakeholders through a series of four co-creation workshops. The outputs of the project could serve as an example for other institutions.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>Researcher diversity is crucial for research quality and impact. It helps address biases, such as gender and ethnic bias. However, the researcher population at VU, like other European institutions, struggles with diversity. The Vrije Universiteit</p>

Amsterdam’s (VU) Recognition and Rewards (R&R) has implemented measures to enhance research quality, aligning with the COARA agreement. However, the program lacks a focus on equality and inclusiveness, critical principles of this agreement. This project will integrate diversity into VU’s research assessment reforms by aligning efforts between the VU R&R program, the Diversity Office, and initiatives across Europe. The primary goal is to co-develop a concrete action plan on how to increase researcher diversity through researcher assessment at the VU. For this, four co-creation workshops will be held. Prior to the first workshop, we will conduct a literature review on barriers and opportunities for increasing diversity through research assessment. The literature review will serve as input for the first workshop, in which we will work together with R&R expert from the different faculties at the VU to identify which barriers and opportunities apply locally and merit further exploration. Using these insights, in Workshop 2, we will invite diverse researchers and diversity topic experts to map at which points in research assessments diversity is impacted, in order to locate opportunities for change. This will serve as input for the next workshop, in which we will work with the same workshop group to develop a first draft of the action plan on how to foster diversity through research assessment reform. In the final workshop, we will refine the action plan through conducting a knowledge exchange with other institutions. The ultimate aim of this project is to contribute towards more equitable and inclusive research assessment processes within and beyond the VU, in line with the spirit of the COARA agreement.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
- Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
- Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Change Project selected n°2

Organisation overview	 Czech Academy of Sciences
Czech Academy of Science Prague, Czech Republic <i>The Czech Academy of Sciences is a complex of 54 public research institutions. Its primary mission is to conduct a wide range of scientific research across various disciplines (mainly natural, technical and social sciences and the humanities)</i>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
New Assessment Tools for Internal Programs of the Czech Academy of Sciences
Abstract
<p>The project focuses on boosting the activities of the Czech Academy of Science (“the CAS”) associated with a new upcoming platform aimed at setting the environment for excellent research which opens the opportunities for the deeper engagement of qualitative assessment tools. The new platform will be complementary to ongoing internal programs of the CAS (“program”) providing support of scientific excellence for selected researchers in all career stages on the 52 CAS research institutes.</p> <p>Within the project, we will review the internal assessment processes of the ongoing programs with particular focus on their sensitivity to ARRA principles that we signed up for.</p> <p>We will develop a new set of assessment tools (including criteria) for new programs and updates for the ongoing programs, and we will implement them into internal procedures.</p> <p>The project enables to accelerate and complement the changes to further improve the CAS assessment practices and create the environment responsive both to the needs of the researchers and the institutes reflecting the global development of research for maximizing the quality and impact of the research.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
The mission is to create appropriate assessment toolbox aligned with the ARRA principles and based on the modern assessment approach for the ongoing and new programs that support diverse research careers, excellent research teams and talented researchers’ development and retention. Change in internal

assessment processes will enable recognition of the diversity of research activities and practices that contribute to research quality and taking into account researchers’ individual contexts and careers. The experiences of the network of COARA members similar to our organisation and also within the CZ and the results of the topic relevant COARA WGs (proposals, responsible indicators) will be used.

The objectives are to create mostly qualitative assessment tools for internal program assessment, i.e.:

- 1) evaluating criteria for individual applicants, project proposals and projects (at three main touchpoints: entry – interim – exit),
- 2) program evaluating criteria((A) – to set measurable KPIs for the program in relation to its goals, (B) – to obtain regular feedback from the research community involved and the key stakeholders about the program to gain inputs for its improvement and development in the future)

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Change Project selected n°3

Organisation overview	<p>Politecnico di Torino</p>
<p>Politecnico di Torino Torino, Italy</p> <p><i>Politecnico di Torino was the first Italian engineering school, and is now a public technical university focusing on engineering and architecture, known for its research and innovation in these fields.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
Title
<p>FEDRA – An institutional FAIR data lake for transparent, inclusive, and reproducible Research Assessment</p>
Abstract
<p>Universities, and as such Politecnico di Torino, have a lot of data about their own research processes, which should be used to measure performance and to devise strategies to progress towards university’s goals. In this respect, institutional data sovereignty is instrumental. The FEDRA project aims at building a proof-of-concept institutional data lake consistent with the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) fed by the multiple university’s databases which store information on several research dimensions (projects, proposals, contracts, patents, publications and data, staff registry, etc.) to enable the creation of indicators and tools for research assessment and self-assessment which, in line with the COARA commitments, shall be multi-dimensional, inclusive, transparent and reproducible. Based on the availability of FAIR research information data, the project aims at producing and testing indicators harvested from meaningful metrics with respect to open science practices and the promotion of gender equality and diversity. These new indicators will be defined and tested leveraging on the work carried out in some of the COARA working groups and by engaging the University’s community with workshops, surveys, and the creation of focus groups tailored on career-stage and disciplines.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>The goal of the project is the development of a proof-of-concept institutional research information data lake implemented according to the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability). The FAIR data lake will be built by leveraging on the experience recently gained with the creation of the</p>

university’s Open Research Registry, fed by multiple internal databases storing information on several research dimensions (projects, proposals, contracts, patents, publications and data, staff registry, to name a few).

A FAIR data lake is instrumental to test indicators, enable meta-research and strategy development, promote transparent and accountable assessment and accelerate the adoption by the Politecnico’s research community of good practices in line with the COARA commitments.

The FAIR data lake demonstrator will be used to carry out two pilot activities engaging the research community: 1) the integration of open science products in the open research registry and the design of a dashboard for open science products to complement that already available for publications; 2) the analysis of the current internal bibliometric indicators disaggregated per gender to grasp the reason of some possible bias issues that emerged during the drafting of the 2023 university’s Gender Balance but whose origin has not been clarified.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Change Project selected nº4

Organisation overview	
<p>Fundació per a la Universitat Oberta de Catalunya Barcelona, Spain</p> <p><i>Open University of Catalonia (Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, UOC) is one of the world's premier online Higher Education Institutions. UOC's core goal is promoting innovative education, personalized lifelong learning, and research and innovation in the intersection between digital technologies and human activity.</i></p>	

The Project	
Type	
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project	
Title	
ECE4CoARA - Effective Community Engagement for a successful CoARA action plan implementation at the Open University of Catalonia (UOC): a community engagement case study at institutional level.	
Abstract	
<p>The ECE4CoARA proposal presented by the Open University of Catalonia (UOC, Spain) aims to fully integrate the CoARA action plan approved last March in the University policies and practices thanks to an active and effective engagement of the University community. Only by bringing the community onboard during the reform process journey and facilitating them to actively participate in the discussions and internal changes of assessment criteria and procedures, the cultural change proposed by CoARA principles and, in particular, by the UOC action plan will be robust and sustainable enough.</p> <p>In addition, a community engagement at institutional level case study will be elaborated based on the deployed activities and the lessons learned during this one-year project. The case study, that will be openly shared, ambitions to be an inspiration for other organisations, mainly Universities, with similar characteristics to the UOC and to increase the CoARA pool of practical resources for the implementation of the action plans.</p>	
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?	
<p>The mission of this proposal is to mature our internal reform process and fully integrate our institutional plan into the University's daily life through an active and effective engagement of our community.</p> <p>The proposal seeks to achieve:</p>	

- Objective 1: a UOC community engaged with/in CoARA. A community that is not only informed of the reform process, but actively takes part in it and contributes to improve, modulate and mature the actions of our plan,
- Objective 2: a solid and sustainable reform process at UOC. Bringing people onboard during the whole process facilitates that the internal changes implemented are more robust and tangible and take into account the diversity and richness of our community,
- Objective 3: a community engagement case study at institutional level. A transparent engagement dynamic that serves as an inspiration to other organisations.

These objectives point directly to the commitments of the Agreement: objective 1 to commitments 7 and 9, objective 2 to 5 and 6, and objective 3 to 8 and 10. In addition, any activity will have as a starting condition the fulfilment of the core commitments of the Agreement as they constitute the baseline from which to build a better evaluation system.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Change Project selected n°5

Organisation overview	
<p>University of Graz Graz, Austria</p> <p><i>University of Graz is Austria's second oldest University, offering a wide range of academic programs, focusing on five fields of excellence - BioHealth, Climate, Europe, Complexity, AI - supplemented by four research networks and is partner in Argus Alliance.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Managing the cultural transition associated with research assessment reform
Abstract
<p>The University of Graz is implementing a comprehensive research assessment reform. The focus is on transparency and recognition of the various academic contributions in the areas of research, teaching, funding, outreach activities, service to the institution and leadership.</p> <p>The reform outlines expectations for academics at different career stages and research branches and rewards them. This reform is a cultural shift in research assessment as it focuses on the quality and impact and the use of qualitative methods in evaluation purposes. It is crucial to address resistance, anxiety and fears around qualitative assessment methods.</p> <p>To address concerns and demonstrate the value of this shift, the University will establish a task force to develop a change management and communication plan, including workshops, focus groups, online resources and reform ambassadors. A shared commitment of all stakeholders, from the rectorate to faculty, administration, funders and external reviewers must be developed by active support and a clear change management process. The alignment of the reform with the university's vision will enable improvement and acceptance of the reform.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>The University of Graz is constantly reviewing its assessment system. Guiding principles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increasing transparency in recruiting, promoting and rewarding researchers/units;

- recognizing the wide range of diverse outputs, practices and activities carried out by researchers to maximize the quality and impact of research;
- to manage the resistance to change, the uncertainty with qualitative methods and the concerns about increased workload.

Up to this assessment processes have relied on quantitative indicators. To gain a more comprehensive understanding of achievements it is essential to build on qualitative forms of judgement. To address concerns about qualitative assessment methods, support is needed to demonstrate the value of qualitative assessment approaches and the responsible use of quantitative indicators. This cultural shift in assessment is a challenge. The success of the reform depends on the commitment of the university management, the acceptance of the new modalities by the employees and the cooperation of the university units in the development and implementation. We will provide the best support for the change process in the first phase by setting up a working group to create a concrete plan for change management that will have a lasting impact. However, change management is ongoing and will continue after the first year

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Change Project selected n°6

Organisation overview	
University of Gdańsk Gdańsk, Poland <i>The University of Gdańsk in Poland offers diverse academic programs and engages in research across various disciplines, with a focus on maritime studies and environmental sciences.</i>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Reform of researchers’ assessment in the University of Gdańsk
Abstract
<p>The assessment of individual researchers should vary according to the specific nature of scientific disciplines, research types as well as researchers career stages. Thus, it is important to maximise the quality and impact of research, considering the full range of research outputs, open science practices and data sharing as well as open collaboration within science and by allowing researchers to contribute to the definition of their research goals and aspirations.</p> <p>Most important part of the project is analysis of strengths and weaknesses of the current assessment system and new challenges among researchers. To prepare for implementation of policy changes preliminary research, surveys, focus group meetings and cooperation with leading experts will be undertaken. The final stage will be the preparation of a new policy, which will be implemented with the support of experts.</p> <p>Project will help develop the research assessment system tailored to address the specific challenges existing in the academic environment. There is a need to extend the theoretical background, with practical solutions offered by the beneficiaries themselves and the knowledge of the assessment experts. All conducted actions will allow to have a solid background for reviewing existing procedures and adapting them to the needs of researchers.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
The University of Gdańsk conducts strategic actions to improve the working conditions of the entire academic community, including ensuring the highest standards of recruitment, assessment and promotion of employees in compliance with the European Charter for Researchers. Due to the expectations of academic community and to reform scientific activities evaluation at the

national level, taking into account the complexity of the assessment, reliability and transparency, University of Gdańsk joined the CoARA coalition in 2023.

The assessment of individual researchers should vary according to the specific nature of scientific disciplines, research types as well as researchers career stages. Thus, it is important to maximise the quality and impact of research, considering the full range of research outputs, open science practices such as early knowledge and data sharing as well as open collaboration within science and by allowing researchers to contribute to the definition of their research goals and aspirations. Therefore, in proposed project, consultations with researchers themselves are very important (e.g. surveys, focus groups), and obtained answers will help develop and create new principles.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Change Project selected n°7

Organisation overview	
<p>Häme University of Applied Sciences Hämeenlinna, Finland</p> <p><i>Häme University of Applied Sciences (HAMK) in Finland is a learning and research community of over 10,000 people shaping the future of bioeconomy, business, design, education, health, and technology. HAMK provides exceptional tools and environments to their students, staff, and partners to work and collaborate to accomplish useful actions.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
Title
<p>Strengthening the Qualitative Criteria for the Researcher Assessment at Häme University of Applied Sciences</p>
Abstract
<p>The objective of this project is to strengthen the researcher evaluation criteria at Häme University of Applied Sciences (HAMK) to better incorporate qualitative metrics, supported by quantitative measures. The project will define these criteria through collaboration with various stakeholders, including researchers at different career stages, supervisors, and the researcher evaluation group. The criteria's integration with the organisation's other processes will also be outlined. A significant focus of the project is on HAMK's strategic emphasis on competence development. To ensure the criteria's high-quality use, internal training will be provided to supervisors and researcher evaluators on applying the criteria and on responsible research evaluation practices. The newly developed criteria will be publicly accessible, promoting transparency and accountability.</p> <p>This initiative is crucial for fostering a culture of continuous improvement and excellence in research. The expected outcomes include enhanced alignment of researcher evaluation with organisational goals, improved researcher performance, and strengthened research quality. By engaging stakeholders in the development process and providing comprehensive training, the project aims to establish a robust and sustainable evaluation framework that promotes fair and transparent assessment of research activities.</p> <p>The project will accelerate the procedural and process change in research assessment and contribute to wider and long-lasting organisational development</p>

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

The mission of the project is to enhance the researcher evaluation criteria at HAMK by focusing on qualitative metrics supported by quantitative measures. The objectives include 1) Defining new evaluation criteria collaboratively with researchers, supervisors, and the researcher evaluation group, 2) Mapping these criteria to HAMK’s organisational processes, 3) Ensuring transparent and accessible publication of the criteria and 4) Providing comprehensive training for supervisors and researcher evaluators. The project aligns with the vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment by promoting a more holistic and fair approach to research evaluation. CoARA emphasizes qualitative assessment, transparency, and the involvement of diverse stakeholders in the evaluation process. By integrating these principles, HAMK’s project supports CoARA’s vision of fostering innovative and responsible research assessment practices. The project’s impact includes improved researcher performance, enhanced research quality, and better alignment of evaluations with organisational goals. The work plan involves stakeholder collaboration for criteria development, process integration, public dissemination of criteria, and targeted training programs. The intended outputs are a sustainable evaluation framework and a culture of continuous improvement in research quality at HAMK.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
- Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
- Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Change Project selected n°8

Organisation overview	
<p>JOANNEUM RESEARCH Forschungsgesellschaft mbh Vienna, Austria</p> <p><i>JOANNEUM RESEARCH Forschungsgesellschaft mbH is one of Austria's largest research institute providing applied research and technology development services. It is specialised in information and production technologies, human technology and medicine, and societal sustainability.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
RAPP – Reforming Assessment Policies and Practices at Joanneum Research
Abstract
<p>JR is committed to CoARA principles, and with the RAPP-project, it will apply them in three selected fields: (i) the assessment of researchers in the specific context of a non academic, applied research organisation. (ii) open science policy and practices in seven different JR-institutes, (iii) the recruitment of researchers and how different career tracks and various contributions to research are taken into account for career-development.</p> <p>We combine a participatory approach with action research to collect data on and identify different practices and cultures within JR institutes, covering Natural, Technical and Social Sciences and simultaneously raise awareness for CoARA and its impact on research assessment. We aim to engage a broad range of stakeholders, from early stage researchers to senior and principal scientists, from heads of research groups and institutes to central management and the supervisory board, the scientific advisory board and owner representatives to increase the impact.</p> <p>First, the status quo of current policies and practices related to excellence, open science and recruiting is assessed collectively. Then this empirical evidence will be assessed in the light of CoARA principles and finally a set of priorities and recommendations for a CoARA Action Plan will be developed through co-creation</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>The RAPP project needs to take into account the nature of JR as non-university research performing organization (RPO). Doing mainly applied research for and</p>

in cooperation with various stakeholders of the research ecosystem (research funding organisations, national authorities or companies) constitutes specific requirements e.g. when it comes to define and measure merit or excellence. The project will focus on three topics: (1) the criteria for excellence, (2) open science (3) recruitment practices at JR.

First, the status quo of relevant policies and practices in these three topics within JR is mapped. In a second step the results of this organizational mapping exercise are analysed in the light of the CoARA principles and commitments with different stakeholders and employees and finally, ideas for next steps and interventions for advancing the reform of research assessment (RRA) are developed co-creatively. Our own research on assessing excellence has demonstrated the importance of developing a common understanding of new concepts to (potential) user groups, so RAPP strives for a participatory, co-creative approach and involves stakeholders from JR management and different researcher groups, intersecting along (academic) age, gender, career stage, function. Finally, the JR-internal findings are validated by engaging with the Austrian non-university research community.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
- Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
- Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Change Project selected n°9

Organisation overview	
<p>Steinbeis Transfer Center Solar Thermal Energy Systems Baden-Baden, Germany</p> <p><i>Steinbeis Transfer Center Solar Thermal Energy Systems is rattached to the Stenbeis international network (spanning 1100+ transfer enterprises) headquartered in Germany. It is specialises in research and development of solar thermal energy technologies, promoting sustainable energy solutions.</i></p>	

Please note that this project has been selected but following the decision communication, they were not responding to any of the contact requests of the CoARA Secretariat. After an investigation for alternative means of setting up contacts and an iterative round of unsuccessful further attempts, the CoARA Secretariat came to the conclusion that the selected project has failed to comply with the contractual requirements for financing the project as set out in the sub-grant agreement (i.e. deadline for signing the subcontract) resulting in the inability to provide funding for the project. Thus, the amount of funding has been deferred to the Cascade Funding call 2.

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
<p>Transforming Research Assessment at the Steinbeis Transfer Center - An Integrated Approach to Responsible and Impactful Evaluation</p>
Abstract
<p>The Steinbeis Transfer Center Solar Thermal Energy Systems (Steinbeis Transferzentrum Solarthermische Energiesysteme, STCSTES) aims to revolutionize its research assessment practices through a comprehensive and integrated reform project. By incorporating 10 carefully selected assessment frameworks and developing a unique classification system, the institute seeks to establish a holistic, evidence-based, transparent, and socially responsible approach to evaluating research quality, relevance, and impact. The project's key objectives include the development of an innovative assessment platform, the implementation of targeted change management and capacity-building initiatives, and the dissemination of best practices to inspire broader reform in the research community. By implementing this ambitious reform, the STCSTES strives to accelerate tangible and sustainable change in its assessment procedures and processes, align its research activities with societal needs and values, and contribute to the advancement of responsible research and innovation practices. The project's comprehensive and integrated approach sets it apart from current efforts and positions the STCSTES as a pioneer and catalyst for transformative change in research assessment. Ultimately, this initiative will</p>

pave the way for a new era of research assessment that prioritizes societal relevance, collaboration, and transparency.

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

The STCSTES’s research assessment reform project aims to transform research evaluation, aligning with the CoARA principles and ARRA commitments. The project’s objectives include recognizing diverse research contributions (ARRA1), adopting a blended qualitative and quantitative multi-dimensional assessment approach (ARRA2), and fostering transparency, collaboration, and societal impact. The work plan involves stakeholder engagement, framework integration, platform development, change management, capacity building, and sustainability planning. It includes creating a holistic, inclusive assessment with unique classification system and an innovative assessment platform tailored to CoARA’s vision (ARRA6). The project emphasizes moving beyond traditional bibliometrics to capture the full spectrum of research contributions and impacts. Stakeholder engagement (ARRA7), capacity building (ARRA8), and dissemination (ARRA9) are central, aligning with CoARA’s commitment to a collaborative research culture. By involving researchers at all career stages, providing training and support, and sharing best practices, the project empowers researchers to engage in responsible, impactful research. Outputs like an integrated assessment platform, training programs, and dissemination materials aim to effect systemic change in research assessment, serving as a model for other organizations embracing CoARA. By adopting a holistic, evidence-based, and stakeholder-engaged approach, the project aligns with CoARA’s vision of a fair, transparent, and impactful research ecosystem.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
- Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
- Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

List of the Cascade Funding Call 1 Beneficiaries: Institutional Pilot Projects

Name of the Project	Organisations	Countries	Pages
Linking the Individual and Collective Responsibility: Transforming the Research Planning and Evaluation Culture	Ilia State University	Georgia	35
CENTRIA COMPETENCES - Developing and piloting the framework for competence management to enhance qualitative research(er) assessment in the university of applied sciences	Centria University of Applied Sciences	Finland	37
TREASURE: Transforming Research Assessment through Responsible Research training of Early Stage Researchers: A pilot study	University of Coimbra	Portugal	39
Impact-based assessment of the translational research in the Italian research hospitals	Association of Healthcare Researchers (ARSI) – Italy	Italy	41
Catalysing research assessment reform in a small and specialist university: Reimagining our Academic Framework and evaluating its implementation in a revised academic performance review exercise	Health Sciences University	United Kingdom	43
Piloting new approaches and metrics for research assessment. A first step for a real transformation.	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	Spain	45
Participatory Diversification of Research Assessment in the Humanities: A Citizens' Council approach	ELTE Eötvös Loránd University	Hungary	47
Assessing the quality of 'non-standard' research outputs in Business and Management: an institutional pilot study	Leeds Trinity University	United Kingdom	49
Qualitative KPIs Tailored for Creative Industries: A Pilot Study on Film-Making, Wearables, and Game Development	Middle East Technical University	Türkiye	51
Towards a Qualitative Paradigm: Rethinking Research and Researchers Assessment at Blanquerna, Universitat Ramon Llull- ReAss	Universitat Ramon Llull Fundacio	Spain	53
Impact Narratives for biomedical research: a Co-creation Approach to fair implementation	Fundacio Centre de Regulacio Genomica	Spain	55

Name of the Project	Organisations	Countries	Pages
Evaluating the Impact of Reformed Research Assessment and the use of Narrative CV's in Academic Career Promotion at Swansea University	Swansea University	United Kingdom	57
Advancing Sofia University St Kliment Ohridski's Research Assessment Towards Open Research (AURA)	Sofia University St Kliment Ohridski	Bulgaria	59

Institutional Pilot Project selected n°1

Organisation overview	
<p>Ilia State University Tbilisi, Georgia</p> <p><i>Ilia State University in Georgia is one of the leading research and educational institutions in Georgia. It offers diverse academic programs (e.g. arts, law, business, natural sciences) and engages in research across various fields, emphasizing innovation and community engagement.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
<p>Linking the Individual and Collective Responsibility: Transforming the Research Planning and Evaluation Culture</p>
Abstract
<p>Ilia State University (ISU) is a distinguished example in the Georgian academic space, pioneering greater autonomy for researchers in planning and evaluating research strategy and targets. However, despite ISU's advancements, the current system remains focused on individual performance and needs better contextualization with respect to team capacities, field-specific factors, institutional goals, and ecosystem contexts.</p> <p>The project will pioneer a new participatory model of research evaluation, a novel approach that tailors diversified and flexible evaluation criteria to each organizational unit (school, research institute). This innovative cyclic evaluation process, informed by a qualitative report, will drive future planning and criteria adjustments. Additionally, an electronic platform will be created to facilitate data generation, aggregation, and transparency for internal and external use, ensuring continuous interaction between evaluation processes and research planning.</p> <p>The model will provide a holistic view of research performance at individual, school, and university levels, fostering collaboration within and between organizational units, researchers, administration, and external actors and facilitating deeper collective reflection on shared goals and contextual challenges</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

Mission – to transform the research evaluation system to better reflect three essential components of ISU’s priorities for research management and CoARA’s vision:

- Underline the importance of contextualization and qualitative input in setting/evaluating targets – considering individual capacities, field-specific factors, institutional goals, and contextual elements within respective ecosystems.
- Balance individual and collective responsibility, emphasizing institutional goals and individual contributions.
- Recognize the interconnected nature of teaching, research, and service, thereby enhancing the holistic view of academic impact.

Goals:

1. Develop and Pilot New Participatory Model of Research Cycle Management:
 - Each organizational unit will develop unique evaluation criteria and targets tailored to research performance complexities and field-specific nuances responsive to institutional and societal contexts.
 - Cyclical evaluation of performance through a participatory approach within and across units.
 - Use results for planning and adjustment of criteria for next cycle.
2. Create Electronic Platform to Support Model Implementation:
 - Facilitate data generation, aggregation, and transparency and ensure linkage between evaluation and planning.
 - Integrate multidimensional quantitative and qualitative data, provide a transparent and holistic picture of research performance at the individual, school, and university levels.
 - Promote collaboration across units, researchers, administration, and external partners to improve research outcomes

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected n°2

Organisation overview	
Centria University of Applied Science Kokkola, Finland <i>Centria University of Applied Sciences in Finland offers multidisciplinary education and applied research services, focusing on fields like engineering, business, and health sciences.</i>	

The Project	
Type	
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project	
Title	
CENTRIA COMPETENCES – Developing and piloting the framework for competence management to enhance qualitative research(er) assessment in the university of applied sciences	
Abstract	
<p>Career paths in Finnish universities of applied sciences (UASs) are still evolving compared to the established paths in universities. Developing researcher profiles is crucial for UASs to enhance their statutory research, development, and innovation (RDI) activities, which focus on development-oriented, interdisciplinary, and applied research. This goal aligns with the CoARA agreement, which emphasizes collaboration and societal impact in research. The CENTRIA COMPETENCES project aims to develop and pilot a competence management framework. This framework will emphasize the variety and importance of different skills, helping personnel navigate their career paths and ensuring research teams possess a diverse range of competences. Additionally, the framework will be useful for recruitment and evaluating salary progression. In the spring 2024, Centria UAS (Centria) renewed its strategy for 2025–2028, closely aligning it with the CoARA action plan to enhance qualitative research(er) assessment. The first CoARA commitment focuses on recognizing the diversity of contributions and careers in research, tailored to the specific needs and nature of the research. This commitment aligns with Centria’s strategic goal of developing a competence management framework to promote expert growth and meaningful work. The framework is also essential for evaluating the impact of research teams and raising scientific standards</p>	
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?	
The CENTRIA COMPETENCES project aims to develop a competence management	

framework highlighting the diversity of research activities and outputs among UAS personnel, emphasizing the equal value of various competences and roles. The CoARA agreement provides UASs an opportunity to elevate applied research as a key part of a researcher's job description and competence portfolio.

The framework will be developed collaboratively with Centria's personnel across different career stages and roles, involving consultations with RDI, education, administration, management and Centria's cooperation group. As a starting point for the framework development, we have identified the following competences:

- RDI (e.g., research, development and innovation tasks across various areas of expertise, peer review of journal articles, open science practices, and integrating RDI with learning)
- Teaching (e.g., pedagogical skills, quantity and quality of teaching, and integrating RDI with learning)
- Networks (collaboration with local, national and international stakeholders and partners)
- Project Administration and Support (e.g., project management, finance, science communication, data management, development of qualitative research(er) assessment, and leadership roles)

Further refinement and identification of additional competences are planned. The framework will serve as a competence management tool for Centria and will be shared with the Finnish UAS network and the CoARA National Chapter

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected nº3

Organisation overview	
University of Coimbra Coimbra, Portugal <i>The University of Coimbra in Portugal is a public institution known for involvement in creation, critical analysis, transfer and dissemination of culture, science and technology.</i>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
TREASURE: Transforming Research Assessment through Responsible Research training of Early Stage Researchers: A pilot study
Abstract
<p>This pilot will develop and test new assessment criteria by allowing early stage researchers (ESRs) who implement specified practices in their thesis research to obtain a “Responsible Research and Open Science” badge alongside their Master/PhD degree. This program will be co-created with University of Coimbra (UC) ESRs and R&D units under supervision and commitment of UC Rectory and Faculties.</p> <p>During the grant, we will form a Local advisory board to define new assessment criteria for responsible research and open science (RROS), co-created with Faculty/R&D unit assessors and the ESRs being assessed; identify institutional and external training to support RROS practices implementation; and involve R&D units in disseminating RROS criteria, strengthening their future assessment by funding agencies. The badge will recognize diverse research outputs. Criteria will be adaptable across disciplines and R&D units. After the grant, we will transform RROS badges into a formal accreditation; adjust hiring criteria for UC entrylevel research positions to recognize the accredited skills; and use RROS criteria to improve research practice and impact.</p> <p>This proposal lays the groundwork to test our hypothesis that reforming ESRs assessments may be a “Trojan horse”, rewarding ESRs for implementing RROS practices, while engaging supervisors to promote widespread culture change.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
This pilot aims to develop and test new assessment criteria by allowing early-stage researchers (ESRs) who implement specified practices in their thesis research to obtain a “Responsible Research and Open Science” (RROS) badge

alongside their Masters/PhD degree. This program will be co-created and piloted with ESRs and University of Coimbra (UC) R&D units. During the grant, we will form a local advisory board to define new assessment criteria for the RROS badge; identify institutional and external training resources to support trainees implementing RROS practices; and involve R&D units in developing and disseminating these criteria, strengthening their future assessment by funding agencies.

After the grant, we will convert the badges into a formal accreditation; adjust hiring criteria for UC entry-level research positions to recognize the RROS badge skills; and use these criteria to improve research practice and impact.

The project aligns with CoARA by recognizing diverse research outputs (e.g. open/reusable protocols, data, code, software); setting criteria that are adaptable across disciplines, R&D units and projects; incorporating qualitative peer review to assess criteria; allocating institutional resources; co-creating criteria with those being assessed; engaging in mutual exchange with an external advisory board and others; and transparently sharing implementation procedures.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
- Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
- Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected n°4

Organisation overview	
<p>Association of Healthcare Researchers, Italy (ARSI) Milano, Italy</p> <p><i>The Association of Healthcare Researchers in Italy (ARSI) is dedicated to advancing healthcare research and fostering collaboration among professionals in the field.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
Title
Impact-based assessment of the translational research in the Italian research hospitals
Abstract
<p>The Istituti di Ricovero e Cura a Carattere Scientifico (IRCCS) are research hospitals distributed across Italy whose mission is to provide prevention, diagnosis, and care according to the latest scientific evidence and evidence to address unmet clinical needs (known as translational research).</p> <p>Nowadays, the core assessment performed every year by the Ministry of Health is based on quantitative metrics like bibliometric indexes, n. registered patents, and funding attraction capacity. The current criteria does not fit the point 2 and 3 of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA). Moreover, the current evaluation system creates a misalignment between the mission of the IRCCS and what is evaluated in practice, thus compromising the effectiveness of research efforts to address the IRCCS mission.</p> <p>We aim to develop a research assessment based on the impact in the real-world, according to the translational science benefit model (TSBM).</p> <p>The project includes the engagement of IRCCS researchers, the online training on the TSBM toolkit, the collection of real-world data on translational research project impact, and a wrap-up meeting to disseminate the results of the pilot study and discuss the scale-up and sustainability of the impact-based assessment with the evaluation representatives of the Ministry of Health.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>The mission of the project is to overcome the current assessment of the translational research in the public Italian IRCCS research hospitals based on quantitative metrics like bibliometric indexes, n. registered patents, and funding</p>

attraction capacity. The current evaluation assessment is not in line with the point 2 and 3 of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) developed by the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). Moreover, it creates a misalignment between the mission of the IRCCS research hospitals and the specific evaluation criteria.

The objective is to move towards research assessment criteria that focus on quality through the development of an impact-based qualitative assessment of the translational research in the Italian IRCCS research hospitals.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
- Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
- Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected n°5

Organisation overview	
<p>Health Science University (ex-AECC University College) Bournemouth, United Kingdom</p> <p><i>Health Sciences University in the United Kingdom is a specialist health sciences institution that aims to create a healthier society through education, research and clinical care, with strengths in applied health, sport, exercise, and social science disciplines.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
<p>Catalysing research assessment reform in a small and specialist university: Reimagining our Academic Framework and evaluating its implementation in a revised academic performance review exercise</p>
Abstract
<p>The project will revise our Academic Framework (AF) to recognise a broader, more diverse range of contributions, activities and behaviours (including open science), and place qualitative judgement at the heart of our academic career assessment procedures. Using the SCOPE framework, a coalition of internal stakeholders, researchers (all career stages) and an external advisor(s) will develop and improve the criteria, tools and procedures aligned to our AF. This will be piloted through our annual performance review exercise, after which we will evaluate the approach and embed the learning in other assessment activities such as recruitment and promotion. Activities will be undertaken throughout to accelerate the understanding and adoption of research assessment reform (RAR) across the university. We will share lessons learned with external organisations/groups. As a small and specialist health sciences university with a nascent but rapidly growing research culture, our experience will be of particular interest to other small and specialist institutions and/or those in the health sciences domain. The project will catalyse our RAR and support our mission to create and sustain a healthy research culture in which researchers are supported to fulfil their potential and the quality and impact of our research are maximised.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

The project’s mission is to raise awareness of the importance of research assessment reform (RAR) across the university, ensure our staff are upskilled in the latest innovations

in academic career assessment (ACA), actively engage a diverse group of staff in RAR (including researchers at all career levels), and accelerate the pace of institutional change at our university. We will revise our Academic Framework (AF) and associated criteria, tools and procedures and test this the annual performance review exercise in 2025. An evaluation will take place of their efficacy, after which we will seek to embed them in other ACA activities, e.g. recruitment and promotion. The project objectives are to:

- Develop the AF to recognise a broader and more diverse range of contributions, activities and behaviours (including open science).
- Evaluate existing and design new tools and procedures to implement the revised AF criteria in the annual performance review exercise, ensuring qualitative judgement at the heart of the process.
- Eradicate inappropriate uses of journal- and publication-based metrics.
- Provide training and development to upskill staff.
- Design and implement an engagement and communication plan to raise internal awareness of CoARA, DORA and RAR.
- Widely promote and discuss lessons learned

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected nº6

Organisation overview	
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona Barcelona, Spain <i>The UAB is a public comprehensive university that contributes to the improvement of society and economic development through a solid educational offer and the generation and transfer of knowledge</i>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Piloting new approaches and metrics for research assessment. A first step for a real transformation.
Abstract
<p>Over the past decade, the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) has actively initiated a process of transformation, connecting education, research and innovation to society and societal challenges. The present proposal aims to fulfil the mission of immersing the UAB community in the main principles of the coalition, invigorating a participatory awareness-raising process, and building the necessary capacities to develop new research assessment processes for closer alignment with the COARA agreement, with the ultimate goal of promoting the quality and impact of UAB research.</p> <p>Beyond the main objective of identifying new approaches and criteria for the research assessment, the pilot, also pursues the objectives of engaging UAB community to discuss and co-create the future steps of the university in the matters aligned with CoARA, as well as to begin the process of training researchers in their roles as researchers and also as evaluators, in order to progressively acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for this new paradigm shift in the evaluation of research.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
Over the past decade, the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) has actively initiated a process of transformation, connecting education, research and innovation to society and societal challenges. The present proposal aims to fulfil the mission of immersing the UAB community in the main principles of the coalition, invigorating a participatory awareness-raising process, and building the necessary capacities to develop new research assessment processes for

closer alignment with the COARA agreement, with the ultimate goal of promoting the quality and impact of UAB research.

The following four objectives have been defined:

- O1. To engage the UAB research community in the transformation process, and create awareness about the new models of research assessment
- O2. To involve members of the UAB research community in proposing new approaches to recognise the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research, and therefore, to define research assessment methodologies primarily on qualitative judgement, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators. Explore opportunities and barriers at institutional level
- O3. To build the capacity within the UAB community on the effective use of the new metrics
- O4. To pilot the new metrics on an existing call, monitoring results and proposing measures for their adoption in institutional policies

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected n°7

Organisation overview	
<p>ELTE Eötvös Loránd University Budapest, Hungary</p> <p><i>ELTE Eötvös Loránd University in Hungary is a public university offering a broad spectrum of academic programs (i.e. archaeology, computer science, life sciences, mathematics, philosophy, physics, social science) and is highly involved in research.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Participatory Diversification of Research Assessment in the Humanities: A Citizens’ Council approach
Abstract
<p>ELTE Eötvös Loránd University is a leading higher education institution in Hungary with outstanding scientific potential. At ELTE’s largest faculty, the Faculty of Humanities, with 18 institutes and 71 departments, a complex system for assessing individual research performance has been developed and implemented. However, the system for assessing academic excellence is based only on quantitative data. This participatory pilot project aims to reform the existing system by developing a qualitatively based recommendation to diversify the assessment of individual researchers from a wide range of disciplines working in the Faculty, focusing on peer review and the societal impact of research. The project is based on an adapted version of the method often used in participatory research, the Citizens’ Jury, which we call the Citizens’ Council. It will be convened from a random sample of the faculty’s research community, stratified by age, gender and academic career stage.</p> <p>Throughout the reform process, the Citizens’ Council develops the qualitative and diversified assessment in a deliberative way and reaches collective decisions. In line with the CoARA Agreement, the members of the Citizens’ Council, with the support of experts, make recommendations for the reform of research assessment, to which the Faculty leadership has committed to respond.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>The aim of this pilot project is to develop a Citizens’ Council of researchers from the Faculty of Humanities of ELTE Eötvös Loránd University in order to propose a reform of individual researcher assessment. The Citizens’ Council is a form of</p>

deliberative mini-public in which a smaller, stratified group of researchers is randomly selected according to age, gender and career stage to deliberate on the reform of research assessment and to make recommendations to the Faculty and the University. To complement the existing approach, of which quantitative research assessment is central, the Citizens' Council will develop a qualitatively based recommendation to diversify the assessment of researchers from a wide range of disciplines working in the Faculty, focusing on peer review and the societal impact of research. In line with the principles and commitments of the CoARA agreement, the project aims to bring deliberation and public participation to decisions on the reform of research assessment through a three-stage process of information, deliberation and recommendation. As a bottom-up initiative, the ELTE Citizens' Council will begin its work against the background of a commitment by the Faculty's management to respond to the proposal for research assessment reform.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected n°8

Organisation overview	
<p>Leeds Trinity University Leeds, United Kingdom</p> <p><i>Leeds Trinity University in the United Kingdom is providing a range of undergraduate and postgraduate programs (e.g. social sciences, health, life sciences, business and computing), with a focus on careers and professional placements.</i></p>	

The Project	
Type	
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>	
Title	
<p>Assessing the quality of ‘non-standard’ research outputs in Business and Management: an institutional pilot study</p>	
Abstract	
<p>This pilot project will explore the potential for fair and robust assessment of ‘non-standard’ outputs in a discipline for which research assessment practices are dominated by the ‘Gold Standard’ of peer-reviewed publications in ‘top tier’ journals, defined by the ABS Academic Journal Guide, FT-100 and other similar ranking systems.</p> <p>Leeds Trinity University Business School is based in the Faculty of Business, Computing and Creative Industries, providing an ideal opportunity to share good practice in assessing multiple types of research output, including literature, poetry, film, photography and digital media. This will be integral to our refreshed Research and Knowledge Exchange strategy for 2024-29.</p> <p>The project will bring together Faculty colleagues to explore how research can be disseminated in diverse ways, and to pilot methods of assessing the quality of such outputs for Business disciplines.</p> <p>Good practice case studies will demonstrate how high-quality Business research can be assessed in diverse ways. We will develop a set of principles and tools that can be used to assess research quality across a range of disciplines and contexts.</p> <p>The project will contribute to the objectives of CoARA by providing evidence-based alternatives to research assessment for disciplines dominated by journal rankings.</p>	
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?	

The mission of the proposed research is to promote the benefits of alternative research assessment methods in a subject area that is heavily influenced by journal ranking systems. The objectives are:

1. To explore how the quality of Business research can be assessed by applying approaches used in other disciplines to assess ‘non-standard’ outputs.
2. To assemble case studies to raise awareness of the potential for fair and robust assessment of ‘non-standard’ outputs in Business and related disciplines.
3. To develop a framework and a set of tools to assist institutions to diversify their approaches to research assessment in disciplines dominated by journal-based or similar ranking methodologies.
4. To lay a basis for wider research and networking to develop this work further across broader disciplinary, institutional and national contexts.

The project aligns closely with the CoARA vision (ARRA, p.2), by:

1. Recognising the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research.
2. Basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, for which peer review is central
3. Influencing decisions about which researchers to recruit, promote or reward

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected n°9

Organisation overview	
<p>Middle East Technical University Ankara, Türkiye</p> <p><i>Middle East Technical University in Turkey is a public technical university specializing in engineering, sciences, architecture and economy.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
Title
<p>Qualitative KPIs Tailored for Creative Industries: A Pilot Study on Film-Making, Wearables, and Game Development</p>
Abstract
<p>Middle East Technical University (METU) proposes an initiative to develop and implement qualitative Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) tailored for assessing research to be held in METU Crea (Center for Research and Innovation in Creative Industries) for the following creative sectors: new-generation film making, game development, and wearable technologies using experiences gathered in METU Crea. METU, with its extensive academic community of over 2,500 academicians, provides a robust foundation for this project. METU Crea supports ecosystem stakeholders across Türkiye, ensuring a broad and significant impact.</p> <p>This project aligns with the ARRA by focusing on qualitative evaluation methods supported by responsibly used quantitative indicators. Through stakeholder workshops and collaboration with external experts, whom we already know from the film, gaming, and wearable technology industries, we will define KPIs that reflect innovation, societal impact, and creative excellence. These KPIs will be piloted in select research projects at METU Crea, with comprehensive training provided to researchers and evaluators. The project will culminate in evaluating and refining the KPIs. Expected outcomes include improved assessment methods, recognition of diverse research outputs, and a scalable model that other institutions can adopt. During the project, we will deep dive into the existing methods developed by CoARA working groups.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>Middle East Technical University (METU) proposes an initiative to develop and implement qualitative Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) tailored for assessing R&D to be conducted at METU Crea (Center for Research and Innovation in</p>

Creative Industries) for the following creative industries and their inter-relations: new-generation film making, game development, and wearable technologies. The mission of the project is to explore qualitative KPIs applicable to R&D practices in these creative industries, their interactions, and their intersections by shifting the focus from traditional quantitative metrics to qualitative assessments that better capture innovation, societal impact, and creative excellence.

Objectives:

1. Develop KPIs reflecting innovation, societal impact, and creative excellence.
2. Pilot KPIs in selected projects at METU Crea to test their effectiveness and adaptability.
3. Conduct training sessions for researchers and evaluators.
4. Gather feedback to refine and improve KPIs, ensuring they meet the needs of all relevant stakeholders.

The intended outputs include improved assessment methods and a scalable model designed to foster a more inclusive and impactful R&D environment. This initiative aligns with CoARA's vision of advancing research quality and impact through responsible assessment practices.

The work plan, feasible within a 12-month, includes clear and achievable milestones, ensuring the project's success and sustainability.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected nº10

Organisation overview	
<p>Ramon Llull University Barcelona, Spain</p> <p><i>Universitat Ramon Llull in Spain is a private university comprising several institutions, offering a variety of academic programs and conducting research in fields like engineering, social sciences, and humanities.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
Title
<p>Towards a Qualitative Paradigm: Rethinking Research and Researchers Assessment at Blanquerna, Universitat Ramon Llull- ReAss</p>
Abstract
<p>This project aims to pilot a reform of research and researcher assessment practices at the Research Institute on Psychology, Learning, and Development at Blanquerna, Universitat Ramon Llull. By aligning with the CoARA principles, we will shift from traditional quantitative metrics to a comprehensive, qualitative evaluation system. This approach will recognize diverse types of research contributions, promote a broad consideration of research quality and societal impact, and foster inclusivity, peer review, openness and collaboration among researchers. The project will involve developing new assessment criteria, training relevant stakeholders within our institution, and implementing pilot evaluations to ensure the new system's effectiveness and sustainability.</p> <p>We want to take advantage of implementing an institutional pilot project to understand the challenges, biases and researchers' attitudes when adopting new research assessment criteria. At the same time, the pilot will allow us to revise the current assessment system and related practices to discern which of those practices are consistent with the new criteria and which need to be revised. Finally, the assessment procedures and criteria are linked to a culture of assessment that has been developed over time in the fields of research specific to Blanquerna's research groups: education, communication, health and sports.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>The mission of this pilot proposal is to transform the assessment of research and researchers at Blanquerna, Universitat Ramon Llull, by adopting a qualitative evaluation framework. This initiative aligns with CoARA's vision to enhance</p>

research quality and impact through diverse, inclusive, and collaborative practices. Our objectives include developing new qualitative assessment criteria, based on a narrative CVs, designing a portfolio in which qualitative indicators of quality were distributed through a diversity of research contributions, conducting training for researchers in our institution at any stage of their careers, and implementing pilot assessments to validate and refine the new system. This pilot reform will drive institutional change, making our assessment practices more comprehensive and aligned with international standards. We are aware that specific efforts and actions over time will be required to revert some of the principles of this research assessment culture mainly based on the productivity of publications on top quality journals and metrics and accept a new culture more grounded on the quality and diversity of research contributions and their societal impact than on the quantity of a reduced type of outputs aligned with CoARA’s vision.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected nº11

Organisation overview	
<p>Fundació Centre de Regulació Genòmica Barcelona, Spain</p> <p><i>Fundació Centre de Regulació Genòmica in Spain is a biomedical research institute focusing on genomics and related areas, aiming to understand complex biological systems and their interaction with the environment.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Impact Narratives for biomedical research: a Co-creation Approach to fair implementation
Abstract
<p>Impact narratives are among the most prominent methods proposed for fairer and more impactful research assessments. Already extensively used in some contexts (for example, the REF system¹ in the United Kingdom), they are being adopted by a growing number of organisations to showcase the societal benefits of science.</p> <p>Their adoption, however, is particularly complicated for basic research; fundamental biology, for example, profoundly influences society, but with hard to-define, complex impact pathways that become clear only years after the original breakthrough. Thus, the concept of “impact outside of academia” is challenged by our scientific community, with many fearing that this new assessment will sideline basic research.</p> <p>As impact narratives start being a requirement for funding bodies, we propose to engage our scientists in co-creation activities with three interlinked objectives: 1) raise awareness on current trends in research assessment and impact evaluation; 2) pilot a workflow for the definition of impact narratives at our institute, defining group of interests, decision-making processes and new indicators; 3) advocate for a more inclusive definition of impact, one that considers the step-by-step approach of basic science and highlights the role of reproducibility and openness in achieving impact inside and outside of academia.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

According to CoARA’s core commitments, the use of diverse, qualitative metrics is crucial in research assessment. Impact narratives could help move the focus to the benefits that research brings to society; however, their implementation is challenging for basic, non-directly-applied research. As a centre for fundamental research, committed to research excellence and Open Science practices, the CRG is uniquely positioned to face new requirements for impact narratives in future evaluations (in our case, stemming from the Catalan funding system). To find a middle ground between the perceptions of our community and the need for reform, we propose a 3-step work plan to: 1) raise awareness on the limits of bibliometric evaluations and the adoption of non-quantitative metrics by several funding agencies; 2) pilot a bottom-up framework to develop future impact narratives of the institute; 3) foster dialogue on the role of open and transparent practices to boost the impact of fundamental science. We will use the results to, on the one side, advocate with external stakeholders and policymakers for a broader definition of impact; and on the other, to pave the way for recognition of impact-linked activities (i.e. public engagement, open science, tech-transfer activities) in our internal evaluation processes.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected n°12

Organisation overview	
<p>Swansea University Swansea, United Kingdom <i>Swansea University, UK has been producing world class research since 1920. We have a long history of working with business and industry but today our research has a much wider impact, reaching across the health, wealth, culture, and well-being of a global society.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
Title
<p>Evaluating the Impact of Reformed Research Assessment and the use of Narrative CV’s in Academic Career Promotion at Swansea University.</p>
Abstract
<p>In 2022 Swansea University began an extensive reform of its Academic Career Pathways (ACPs) and Research Assessment. Our goal is to better recognise contributions and outcomes that maximise the quality and impact of academic careers, basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.</p> <p>Academic staff were involved in the reform process and in developing new process for academic career assessment. We have removed narrow, quantitative KPIs from the promotion process, and have included two core components, alongside contributions to education and research: innovation, engagement & enterprise; and collegiality, leadership & management. Within research, we include recognition of Open Research for the first time. The reformed process will be implemented for staff applying for promotion from September 2024. Evaluation of the reformed process is essential.</p> <p>The purpose of the Cascade application is to establish and implement a process for evaluating the impact of career pathway transformation. We propose to adopt and adapt the Self-Evaluation Framework co-developed by the UKRI Alternative Uses Group (https://zenodo.org/records/8060614) through surveys with both applicants and reviewers. Using this open framework we will capture anonymised data, share and compare best practice and lessons learned through anonymised findings with CoARA, the UK Chapter and UKRI communities.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

Swansea University’s reformed Academic Career Pathways assessment (2024) and the process for their implementation align directly with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. The mission of this proposal specifically addresses commitment 10, to evaluate practices, processes and tools, and to make interoperable anonymized data openly available for research on research into narrative CVs for academic assessment during promotion. The time-bound specific objectives of the proposal, following from invitations to apply for promotion, are to

1. Undertake Process evaluation of resources and support provided to applicants, panels and reviewers (December 2024 – June 2025).
2. Explore the impact on Responsible Assessment to understand how the narrative CV is being used by reviewers and panels, and how this is changing the way research is assessed and recognised (January – July 2025).
3. Make the evaluation transparent, creating and sharing anonymised evidence gathered from using a Framework co-created between academics and funders of research (August 2025).
4. Understand how the narrative CV is being completed and assessed, to support continuous improvement and to make improvements in support of Responsible Assessment (September 2025).

Aligned to commitment 8, we will share best practice and lessons learned across CoARA and wider research communities.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Institutional Pilot Project selected n°13

Organisation overview	
<p>Sofia University St Kliment Ohridski Sofia, Bulgaria</p> <p><i>Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski in Bulgaria is a public university providing diverse academic programs (e.g. law, education, theology, physics, biology, medicine, history) and has been granted the « HR Excellence in Research » award in 2019.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
Title
<p>Advancing Sofia University St Kliment Ohridski’s Research Assessment Towards Open Research (AURA)</p>
Abstract
<p>The AURA project will explore the attitudes of academics and researchers from Sofia University towards expanding research assessment and incorporating the open research dimension into it. Via a co-creation process, the project will establish how the research-active members of Sofia University see open research fit to be included in the current research assessment and promotion procedures. The project will also engage the Ministry of Education and Science and the National Evaluation and Accreditation Agency of Bulgaria in an important dialogue with policymakers and assessors.</p> <p>The proposal addresses a current gap in the research assessment in Bulgaria. On the one hand, in May 2024, a new law on research was enacted, the first national legislation placing open research at the core of scientific enquiry and policies. On the other hand, research assessment is regulated by the Law on Academic Staff Development in the Republic of Bulgaria; each academic institution has rules of operation and a code of practice in place, which could set additional conditions and/or requirements for academics. AURA seeks to inform the institutional Code of Practice but also proposes a blueprint for national reform in assessment, integrating adequately and supporting open research.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>AURA is an institutional pilot project which aims to involve academics from Sofia University St Kliment Ohridski (SU) in Bulgaria in the co-creation of a framework which will integrate for the first time in Bulgaria components of open science into research assessment. The mission of the proposal is to provide national</p>

leadership in research assessment reform which brings open science into the assessment framework. AURA’s objectives are to:

- Catalyse the integration of open research into the research assessment within SU.
- Gradually prepare SU to join the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and make the Agreement's efforts more visible to Bulgarian stakeholders.
- Facilitate the identification, development, and capacity building, leading to the exchange of emerging good practices for adding an open research dimension to the research assessment at SU.
- Develop recommendations for integrating a new research assessment component reflecting open research in SU and national recommendations for the legislative framework on research assessment.

These objectives are fully consistent with COARA mission and the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment